

Spectrophotometric determination of cerium(IV) using potassium ferrocyanide as an analytical reagent

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Abstract : Potassium ferrocyanide is used in the determination of cerium(IV) spectrophotometrically. It forms a greenish yellow complex in dilute acetic acid solution with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 425 nm. The method is free from interference of a large number of metal ions. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the formed complex are $6.0 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.023 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, cerium(IV), potassium ferrocyanide.

There has been a considerable interest in the trace determination¹ of lanthanide elements because of their similarities in chemical behaviour. This causes problems in their estimation due to their frequent interference with each other. Cerium(IV) forms more stable complex than cerium(III) and other trivalent lanthanides. This behaviour of the element is utilized in working out a simple method for the microdetermination of cerium(IV) by its complexation with potassium ferrocyanide in aqueous solution.

Experimental

Standard stock solution of cerium(IV) containing $1 \text{ mg ml}^{-1} \text{ Ce}^{\text{IV}}$ is prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) in minimum volume of dilute H_2SO_4 and standardized volumetrically². Working solutions at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level are obtained by suitable dilutions. Solutions of other metal ions are prepared by dissolving their commonly available "chemically pure" salts in distilled water or dilute hydrochloric or sulphuric acid. One percent solution of potassium ferrocyanide is prepared in distilled water. 1 M solution of acetic acid is used. Shimadzu-UV-140-02 UV-Visible spectrophotometer is used for spectral measurements.

Procedure : To a solution containing $50 \mu\text{g}$ of Ce^{IV} in a 10 ml measuring flask, add 1 ml 1 M CH_3COOH , 2 ml 1% $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ and the contents are heated to 55–62 °C. The greenish yellow complex thus formed is cooled and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance measurements of the coloured species are taken at 425 nm against the similarly prepared reagent blank using 10 mm matched cells on a UV-Visible spectropho-

tometer. In order to draw a standard curve, different microgram amounts of the metal ion are taken in each set and their corresponding absorbance values are noted following the procedure and the graph is plotted between the two variables.

Results and discussion

In dilute acid solution, cerium(IV) forms a greenish yellow complex with potassium ferrocyanide whose absorption maximum lies at 425 nm. The absorbance measurements are taken in the aqueous phase as the resulting complex is non-extractable in nature.

The absorbance of the complex is influenced by temperature and reagent concentrations as shown in Table 1.

It is evident from the study that for $50 \mu\text{g Ce}^{\text{IV}}$, 0.9–1.5 ml of 1 M acetic acid and 1.9–2.2 ml of 1% $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ at 55–62° in 10 ml aqueous solution are the optimum conditions for the formation of the complex ($\lambda_{\max}$ 425 nm).

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of diverse ions/complexing agents on the absorbance of the complex is studied. Sulphate, oxalate, nitrate, acetate, citrate, fluoride, sulphosalicylic acid, thiourea, 5 mg each; chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrite, 2 mg each; thiocyanate, 0.5 mg; tartrate, EDTA, 0.1 mg each; phosphate, 0.05 mg; added prior to the addition of the reagent to the aqueous phase in a final 10 ml volume do not affect the absorbance of the Ce^{IV} -ferrocyanide complex.

From the study of cationic effect on the Ce^{IV} complex, it is inferred that Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Os^{VIII} ,

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the cerium complex

Temp (°C)	30	35	40	50	53	55-62	63	65	70
Absorbance	0.040	0.060	0.100	0.175	0.200	0.210	0.205	0.190	0.150
[AcOH, 1 M] ml	0	0.5	0.7	0.9-1.5	1.7	2.0	2.5	3.0	
Absorbance	0.075	0.160	0.200	0.210	0.205	0.200	0.195	0.190	
{K ₄ [Fe(CN) ₆], 1% (ml)}	0	0.5	1.0	1.5	1.7	1.9-2.2	2.5	3.0	
Absorbance	0.010	0.075	0.140	0.190	0.200	0.210	0.200	0.190	

Re^{VII}, Ru^{III}, Pr^{III}, La^{III}, Eu^{III}, Nd^{III}, Gd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Tb^{III}, Dy^{III}, Y^{III}, 1 mg each, Cr^{VI}, Th^{IV}, 0.5 mg each; As^{III}, Ti^{III}, V^V, W^{VI}, Cd^{II}, Hg^I, Zr^{IV}, Nb^V, Mo^{VI}, Fe^{II}, U^{VI}, Tl^{III}, Sn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, 0.1 mg each; in 10 ml aqueous solution, do not practically influence the absorbance.

The absorption spectrum of Ce^{IV} complex shows absorption maxima at 425 nm (Fig. 1). The complex is quite stable and obeys Beer's law in the range upto 0-12 µg Ce m/l and the optimum concentration range that can be measured, as evaluated from Ringbom plot³, is 2.5-10.0 µg/ml. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are 6.0 × 10³ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.023 µg Ce cm⁻², respectively. The relative error of the method is found to be 1.1%. For eight replicate determinations containing 50 µg cerium each time, the standard deviation is ±0.001 when the absorbance measurements are effected within 35 min.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of Ce^{IV}-ferrocyanide complex (A) Ce^{IV} 5 µg ml⁻¹ measured against reagent blank, (B) reagent blank measured against distilled water. Formation of complex at 55-62 °C, measurement of absorbance after cooling to room temperature.

Stoichiometry of the complex The ratio of Ce^{IV} to ferrocyanide in the complex is determined as 1 : 1 by Job's method of continuous variations employing their equimolar solutions and this ratio is further confirmed by the mole ratio method⁴. The complex is an ion pair, Ce⁴⁺. Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻.

Conclusion :

The proposed method of determination of trace amounts of cerium is quite simple and is free from the interference of a large number of metal ions including other lanthanides. The validity of the method is tested by analyzing different samples of varying composition as given in Table 2.

Table 2. Analysis of some synthetic sample mixtures containing cerium by the proposed procedure

Composition of the sample (amount in mg)	Ce ^{IV}	Ce ^{IV}
	added (µg)	found (µg)
Y ^{III} (0.8), Sm ^{III} (0.4)	50	51
Tb ^{III} (0.6), Ho ^{III} (0.5)	40	42
Eu ^{III} (0.7), Ho ^{III} (0.4)	30	30
La ^{III} (0.5), Pr ^{III} (0.5), Nd ^{III} (0.5)	60	61
Dy ^{III} (0.05), Gd ^{III} (0.5), La ^{III} (0.5)	30	30
Co ^{II} (0.5), Ni ^{II} (0.5), Cu ^{II} (0.5)	40	42
V ^V (0.05), Mn ^{II} (0.1), Os ^{VIII} (0.5)	50	51
Cr ^{VI} (0.2), Re ^{VII} (0.5), La ^{III} (0.5)	45	46

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